

D2.1 Mixed-Media Research Corpus

*A short-list of cultural sources for Horizon Scanning
on human-waters relations*

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1. Introduction

In contribution to the European Union Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030¹, the FLOW project studies young generations' relations and engagement with oceans and waters². Through the FLOW project, our research aims to gain better insights into how European youth **shape and hold their expectations** about the futures of the ocean, seas and waterways. This includes deepening knowledge about how youth understand **human-water relationships, how emotional associations with water might be formed, and in what ways youth come to value these waters** when considering the present and future states of Europe's diverse water ecologies.

The foresight study (WP2) examines a variety of cultural sources for signals and drivers of change that are influencing popular and peripheral expectations, hopes and fears of younger generations regarding present and future human-water relationships. The FLOW project's Horizon Scanning approach focuses on identifying signals of change evidenced in cultural practices and products, sources are collected through different modes of research and organized in a systematic way. In an iterative process, researchers of the consortium and members of FLOW's Youth Advisory Board identify cultural sources (books, music, movies/series, artworks, social media channels as well as educational, religious/spiritual, leisure and occupational activities), which portray or enact human-water relations.

This deliverable outlines how cultural sources are collected and explicates the underlying search strategy. It provides a list of search strategies - called "*streams*" - that constitute the project's Mixed-Media Research Corpus (D2.1), with the subsequent approach for analyzing the sources and interpreting signals will be described in a later report (D2.3).

2. Horizon Scanning

Horizon Scanning is an approach to detect, identify, gather and organize *signals* that provide insights into possible developments and change processes³. Signals are understood as small pieces of information, data, representations, and other knowledge artifacts that introduce or discuss little known topics that are indicative of future change. In the field of foresight and futures studies, it is assumed that small changes may stabilize over time, thereby obtaining public expression in media or cultural practices⁴ that signal and reinforce medium- to long-term trends driving social change.⁵ As a foresight method, Horizon Scanning aims to sensitize for these possible, emergent changes that signals imply. In additions to signal identification and classification, Horizon Scanning includes processes for their evaluation and analysis.⁶ It is crucial to understand and clarify what an information is a signal for.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en retrieved: 07.06.2023

² www.flowhorizon.eu

³ Cuhls, K. E. (2020). Horizon Scanning in Foresight—Why Horizon Scanning is only a part of the game. *Futures & Foresight Science*, 2(1), e23.

⁴ Hiltunen, E. (2008). Good Sources of Weak Signals: A Global Study of Where Futurists Look For Weak Signals. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 12(4), 21-44.

⁵ Amanatidou, E., Butter, M., Carabias, V., Könnölä, T., Leis, M., Saritas, O., & van Rij, V. (2012). On concepts and methods in horizon scanning: Lessons from initiating policy dialogues on emerging issues. *Science and Public Policy*, 39(2), 208-221.

⁶ Könnölä, T., Salo, A., Cagnin, C., Carabias, V., & Vilkkumaa, E. (2012). Facing the future: Scanning, synthesizing and sense-making in horizon scanning. *Science and public policy*, 39(2), 222-231.

Signals can be collected in different ways, as outlined by Hines et al. (2019)⁷, but there are some general procedures that apply in any Horizon Scanning activity. The first step is the formation of a scan team that accounts for a diversity of competencies and backgrounds. The scan team develops a search strategy may taking into account (partially) automated approaches, conceptual systems, interviews with thought leaders and suitable sources. The search strategy is operationally prepared by establishing a suitable scanning infrastructure (especially IT tools) and defining scanning processes. Optionally, a connection to existing knowledge management systems and digital communication tools. Depending on the phenomena under investigation, methods to compose a collection of signals may consist of interviews, literature reviews or fringe source analyses. In general, we can differentiate between four modes: undirected viewing, conditioned viewing with sensitized areas of concern, enacting and searching with detailed search goals.⁸ Both "undirected-" and "conditioned-viewing" modes entail an open and collaborative approach, i.e. crowdsourcing - wherein a group of people with different perspectives work together to collect signals on a specific topic based on their personal judgement. The modes of "enacting" and "searching with detailed search goals" typically consist of applying an operationalized search strategy to structure the scanning process.

Another increasingly important approach to collect signals is to screen large amounts of both structured (e.g. patent databases or scientific papers) and unstructured (e.g. social networks or news sites) sources with automatized algorithms that use Natural Language Processing (NLP) to find patterns of change (topic modelling).⁹ These automated systems are able to process large volumes of data, but their results require additional human review and assessment before the results can be useful.

Throughout the scanning process, signals are captured and assessed by the scan team. Some signals are selected to be "candidates" for follow up research, given their applicability to the knowledge interests of the project. These signals are often organized according to pre-defined criteria, though new criteria may also emerge during the scanning and signal assessment processes.

Signals are related to each other and bundled into topic clusters. Emerging issues are anticipated and their implications are assessed with regard to the research interest, their opportunities and risks. Optionally, in-depth studies can be conducted on individual topics relevant in terms of future developments. Whatever method is used to collect signals, the identification of potentially emerging changes will always involve interpretative moments where involved actors co-construct what the signals mean.¹⁰ Reflecting on the hermeneutics entailed in this process and allowing for the inclusion of different perspectives through participatory sense-making can limit the risk of overtly biased conclusions.

3. Horizon Scanning in FLOW

Through Horizon Scanning, FLOW develops a forward-looking perspective. By scanning cultural sources concerned with human-water relations, the Horizon Scanning aims to identify and analyze signals of change. The Horizon Scanning's scope is focused on relational aspects. This is a rather untypical scope for Horizon Scanning, which often focuses on clearly defined domains such as technology. To cope with

⁷ Hines, P., Yu, L. H., Guy, R. H., Brand, A., & Papaluca-Amati, M. (2019). Scanning the horizon: a systematic literature review of methodologies. *BMJ open*, 9(5), e026764.

⁸ Choo, C. (2001), *Environmental scanning as information seeking and organisational learning*. *Information Research*, 7(1).

⁹ Tsakalidis, A., Boelman, E., Marmier, A., Gkoumas, K., & Pekar, F. (2021). Horizon scanning for transport research and innovation governance: A European perspective. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 11, 100424.

¹⁰ Aaltonen, M. (Ed.). (2007). *The third lens: Multi-ontology sense-making and strategic decision-making*. Ashgate Publishing, Ltd..

this challenge, the Horizon Scanning in FLOW merges multiple different data sources and search strategies for collecting signals.

3.1 Guiding hypothesis and approaches

The most important set of data to scan for signals on human-waters relations is constituted by cultural sources. **This search strategy builds on the hypothesis that human-waters relations, especially within the young generations, are both portrayed and enacted by cultural expressions, practices and products.**¹¹ Thus, our hypothesis consists of two assumptions:

- (1) Cultural sources, such as literature (e.g. books, magazines), games or movies, present a particular alertness for change. They depict signals that are potentially (trans-)formative for human-water relations (culture as description).
- (2) Cultural sources inspire and support the shaping of human-water relations. They enact relationship types, values, emotions, expectations, hopes and fears (culture as inscription).

The scanning of cultural sources is implemented along different streams. Streams help to search for signals along two criteria: media type (e.g. books) and indicator-based category (e.g. popular). The combination of these two criteria makes up a stream (e.g. popular books).

3.2 Search strategy for cultural sources

The search strategy and categorization evolve iteratively with the collection of potential sources for signals. **The starting point is a collaborative, open scanning process.** In this phase, the scan team composed of researchers and assistants of the FLOW consortium starts to gather signals that are deemed relevant from a personal point of view (cf. conditioned viewing with sensitized areas of concern on p. 4) and record them in a collaborative database. Relevance is assigned based on the following three questions:

- Can this be considered (part of) a cultural expression, practice or product?
- Is this about humans' relations to oceans, rivers, lakes, water?
- Is it plausibly reaching the young generations or is it even shaped by young voices?

When capturing a signal, researchers provide the following information:

- Title for signal
- Description
- Media type
- Reason to include
- Relationship type categorization
- Additional information in regard to authors, links, specific age-groups and more

In parallel to the open scanning, results from the work in WP1 are used, especially from the Open Access transdisciplinary dataset, namely the FLOW Encyclopædia (D1.1)¹² and the inFLOW lens (D1.2). These provide **key literature, concepts, theories and data, which are integrated into the pool of potential sources to screen for signals.**

As the database grows, categories are developed inductively and assigned to each signal. Among other categories that were developed, an important differentiation that can be made is between **popular vs.**

¹¹ A theoretical grounding of this hypothesis will be developed in a later working paper (D2.3).

¹² Mashiur, Z., Borit, M., van den Born, R. J. G., van Heel, B. F., Jónás, K., Priebe, M., Rosa, A., Warnke, P., (2023). FLOW D1.1. Open Access Transdisciplinary dataset: FLOW Encyclopædia. Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.8068069

fringe signals, which provides a more structured way of scanning. While the former accounts for signals taken from cultural sources that are relevant because they have a large reach, the latter are important since they stem from avant-gardist lead-user¹³ or expert sources¹⁴, or because they address a bioregional niche topic. Table 1 depicts this categorization.

Table 1 Categories and indicators used to structure the emerging signal collection. These categories were used to develop the streams included in the Mixed-Media Research Corpus (p. 7).

Category	Indicators
Popular Signal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Bestseller list – High number of views – Rankings – Award and prizes
Fringe Signal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Observation by lead user – Observation by field expert – Credible curation – Bioregional content

The created categories are combined with each other to develop streams that guide the search for specific cultural sources. Streams help to focus attention of the scanning activity on specific sources (cf. searching with a detailed search goal, on p. 4).

4. Mixed-Media Research Corpus

In parallel to the scanning and fine-tuning of the search strategy, the Mixed-Media Research Corpus takes shape (figure 1). **The Mixed-Media Research Corpus is a comprehensive and dynamic list detailing the streams of cultural production that we scan for signals.** It assures that signals are collected in a structured and issue-related manner, while providing the flexibility to adapt and appropriate criteria throughout the Horizon Scanning in WP2. As a dynamic list of streams of cultural production, the corpus will also be reflected by the Youth Advisory Board. Its members will rank the streams under observation based on how well they know the streams (e.g. not known, heard of it, well known), eventually add streams and contribute signals through observing streams.

¹³ Here understood as people that are indicative due to their early adoption of, or consistent engagement with, emerging phenomena in a certain field.

¹⁴ Here understood as field experts that may present a credible source on emerging changes due to their professional perspective and activities surrounding the topic.

Developing the Mixed-Media Research Corpus

Figure 1 The Mixed-Media Research Corpus is first constructed inductively on the basis of categories emerging from the open scanning. These categories are then combined to define streams which are to be scanned. The list of streams constitutes the corpus. In the corpus, all signals are categorized and connected a stream.

4.1 Streams in the Mixed-Media Research Corpus

The current version of the Mixed-Media Research Corpus comprises of the following 33 streams, as listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Mixed-Media Research Corpus

#	Stream	Media	Popular	Fringe
1	Literature on human-waters relations from bestseller-list	Books	x	
2.	Literature and or news articles with bioregional content on human-waters relations	Books/ News articles		x
2. 1	Black Sea			x
2.	Mediterranean Sea			x

2				
2. 3	Bay of Biscay, Iberian Coast, Macaronesia			x
2. 4	North Sea			x
2. 5	Baltic Sea			x
2. 6	Arctic			x
2. 7	Inland			x
3	Literature by field experts on human-waters relations	Books		x
4	Avant-gardist, niche books on human-waters relations	Books		x
5	Video games with a high ranking on gaming platforms (steam, ps)	Video games	x	
6	Niche video games on human-waters relations	Video games		x
7	Popular TikTok influencers on human-water relations	Social media	x	
8	News articles on legal status of seas and waters	News articles	x	
9	Movies on human-waters relations with prizes and awards	Movies	x	
10	Institutional art projects on human-waters relations	Art projects	x	
11	Movies on human-waters relations in production in 2023 (imdb)	Movies		x
12	Most downloaded songs on human- waters relations (spotify)	Music	x	
13	Episodic Children’s Programming (Series)	Serial Program		
14	Episodic Young Adult Programming (Series)	Serial Program		
15	Single exhibition pieces in museums, galleries, fares or alike on human-waters relations	Exhibition		x
16	Large exhibitions in museums, galleries, faires or alike on human-waters relations	Exhibition	x	
17	Popular sea-food trends in 2023	News articles	x	
18	Research on future food from waters	Research articles		x

19	Popular sports and leisure activities on, in and by the water in 2023	News articles	x	
20	Social movements engaged with human-waters relations	News articles		x
21	Fashion that portrays or mimics under water life	Fashion catalogues		
22	Toys that show human-waters relations	Toy catalogues		
23	Exhibits in zoos, aquaria, or a like on human-water relations	Exhibition	x	
24	Documentaries on (aquatic) nature, ranging from wonders of nature to environmental issues	Documentaries	x	
25	Human-water relations used in marketing	Commercials	x	
26	Board games on human-waters relations	Board games		x
27	Analog games with high ranking on games platform (Boardgamesgeek.com)	Games	x	
28	Live Action Role-Playing Games (LARPs) including human-water relations	Games		x
29	Most-played mobile phone games by player count on human-waters relations	Games	x	
30	News from religious/spiritual entities (e.g., The European Christian Environmental Network of the Conference of European Churches; The Islamic Foundation for Ecology and Environmental Sciences; LM International)	News articles	x	
31	News from education entities (e.g., European Marine Science Educators Association) on aquatic ecosystems	News articles	x	
32	Educational curriculum content on aquatic ecosystems	Curriculum on selected countries	x	
33	Socio-technical imaginaries and visions in blue economy	Advertising	x	

Continuous scanning of these structured streams allows for gathering relevant signals for the collection and limits the influence of personal biases in the selection process. The signal collection that arises from the scanning based on the corpus can be complemented by additional streams.

4.2 Additional streams

To ensure that the cultural sources identified are meaningful to the young generations, feedback is provided by the Youth Advisory Board. This board consists of 14 young people from 18 to 29 years from seven different regions in Europe. The board is diversified regarding gender as well as cultural,

geographical and social positionality. **Members of the Youth Advisory Board provide feedback on, contribute to and rank the cultural sources scanned.** Thereby they support (de-)prioritizing cultural sources and identifying signals.

While this focus on culture provides the fundamental base for FLOW's horizon scanning, it is not a rigid structure. The search strategy is flexible towards adapting and appropriating other sources. **Continuous topic modeling performed on an international news database (News API) provides additional sources for identifying signals.** This approach allows for scanning large sets of news articles and semi-automatically develops topics that align with human-waters relations. This does not necessarily widen the scope of horizon scanning in FLOW but broadens the pool of data from which to identify signals. It allows integration of signals that are not merely based on cultural sources, but also consider other fields such as economics (e.g. blue economy).

Horizon Scanning Collecting Signals of Youth-Water Relations from Cultural Sources

Figure 2 Cultural sources are scanned along the streams provided in the Mixed-Media Research Corpus. If deemed relevant (see p. 5) it qualifies as a signal and is added to the database (signal collection).

5. Insights into the preliminary signal collection

At the time of developing the Mixed-Media Research Corpus, the preliminary collection lists 116 signals. A snapshot of the list (figure 3) provides insights into the ongoing work of collecting and organizing the

signals in a collaboratively shared database. Figure 4 depicts the current distribution of media types in our signal collection.

Title	Description	Selection reasons (quality)	Category (type of relationship portrayed)	Media type	Region
10 Marine geoengineering	Marine geoengineering is defined as "a deliberate intervention in the marine environment to manipulate natural processes, including to...	policy-related issues	Stewardship Pollution		Global
11 SAFE: A collection of works exploring safer futures	These 10 projects, created in response to 10 LRF-supported research projects, are rooted in real-world test cases and near-future trends...	credible curators	climate change multi-species more than human	Movie/series Exhibition	Global addr
12 The Legal Rights Of Rivers	Rivers in New Zealand, Australia, India and Colombia have all been granted legal rights recently. Environmental law expert Dr Erin O'D...	observed by field experts	more than human	Podcast/interview	Global
13 Mar Menor gets legal rights as a 'person'	Mar Menor Bay in Spain. Polluted. Ecological Problems. Now thanks to civil society action and pressure Parliament grants new status...	number of downloads, sets, views credible curators	Stewardship more than human	Law/legal text	Spain, Medi
14 Publishing House and Art Installation 'The Consolida'	Reading group: Environment conceived by David Bergé and guests for reading and writing in the proximity of others, inspired by lyrics	credible curators	Stewardship memory culture	Exhibition Publishing Hou...	Greece, liter
15 Fishing with Khabane 'Khabay' Lame TikTok influence	apparently most followed person on TikTok. Born 2000 Senegalese-Italian	number of downloads, sets, views youth-centred content	Influencer	Social media	Global, 80V
16 Sustainability Influencer Agency 'The earth issue'	Ocean Resources Films, young creative activists.	number of downloads, sets, views youth-centred content	Influencer artist intersectional	Podcast/interview Website	Global
17 Seawalkers	Children-book. Popular novel series in which protagonists can shift shapes from human to animal	bestseller lists youth-centred content rankings	Stewardship multi-species more than human		German-spe
18 Abzoi (and potentially other games)	Abzoi is an adventure video game developed by Giant Squid Studios and published by 505 Games for PlayStation 4, Windows, Xbox Or...	number of downloads, sets, views rankings	multi-species screen literacy	Video game	Global
19 The swarm (der Schwarm)	The Swarm (German: Der Schwarm, translated in 10 other languages) is a science fiction novel by German author Frank Schätzing. It...	bestseller... awards etc... number of downloads, sets, views	more than human nature bites back	Book Movie/series	Global
20 Extrapolations	Human non-human conversations with a translating device in a underwater lab. 'Extrapolations' is a brading drama from writer, direc...	number of downloads, sets, views	more than human		Global
21 Terra Nil	'Terra Nil is an intricate environmental strategy game about transforming a barren wasteland into a thriving, balanced ecosystem. Bring...	number of downloads, sets, views rankings	Stewardship education Pollution conservation technology	Video game	Global
22 How to make an Ocean installation art	installation art	credible curators	memory culture artist	Exhibition	Global
23 Monstrous ED-Moby Dick as an AI Model	Monstrous is a contingent, improvised performance, lecture and creative experience which will incorporate music, poetry and discussion	credible curators subjective observation	education technology		Europe
24 'Historic moment' for nature as Europe's first wild ri	Guardian Article	number of downloads, sets, views credible curators	conservation	Article	Albania
25 Futures Images of humans from 12 to 17 and 18-2	Humanism Way Of Future If one thinks it over, then the year 2000 is farther from us than 2040. The time flies extremely fast. Minute s...	youth-centred co... subjective obser... observed by lead...	Stewardship futures maps	Website	Focus on Gr
26 Talk to me about Water- Activist Group	Talk to Me About Water is a playful practice to expand conversations about global water issues.	credible curators subjective observation	activist	Group	Mainly US
27 The Optidan of Lampedusa: A Novella Based on a T	Novella based on a true account of an optician who encountered migrants on a capsizing boat near Lampedusa, and how he rescued s...	credible curators	biogeographical content rankings migration artist	Book	Italy, Medi
28 Water as a topic in "Sendung mit der Maus"	Recently, one of the most popular children series in Germany "die Sendung mit der Maus" has opened a dedicated section on water on...	number of downloads, sets, views credible co... youth-centred...	Stewardship Pollution ocean literacy conservation	Movie/series Website	Germany, A
29 Avatar 2 Ways of water	Blockbuster, especially popular with youngsters. Interesting, the sea people depicted in the movie were inspired by ethnographic work	bestsel... awards etc... number of downloads, sets, views	bestseller more than human	Movie/series	Global
30 Radical Ocean Futures	This project is founded on the belief that sometimes science fiction might succeed where scientific papers fall short. It blends art and sc...	credible curators observed by lead... observed by field ex...	Stewardship multi-species more than human ocean literacy	Exhibition Web... podcast	Sweden, Sc
31 '3 Tage am Meer'	the sea as a place of longing ("for finding yourself")	number of downloads, sets, views	see as a place of longing	music	German-spe
32 In der Natur	humans do not fit into nature	number of downloads, sets, views	nature bites back nature-culture divide	music	German-spe
33 Youth literature section in Berliner library	I found book series like Rick Nautilus and Ocean City for the younger and books for teens and older like Im Meer schwimmen Krokodil	bestseller lists credible curators youth-centred content	migration talent at board	Book	Global
34 New Eels for the Spree river	more than 2 mio. Eels were set free in the Spree river around Berlin after they were caught around a French estuary flowing into the At...	biogeographical content observed by field experts	conservation eco-system management	Article	Rivers arou
35 Rewilding Europe	Is a European network. 'Rewilding' is a progressive approach to conservation. It's about letting nature take care of itself, enabling natur...	biogeographical content observed by lead users	Stewardship more than hu... conservati... eco-system managem...		Danube anc
36 Revival of Guinguette (French River Beach Bars)	Today guinguettes are objects of nostalgia. The guinguettes were marvelous places to return to lighter times during the Années folles	subjective observation	enjoy calm and beauty of waters		France
37 Our Planet	Documentary series created in collaboration with WWF and Netflix. 'Our Planet' shows the wonders of nature as we are all a part of the...	awards and prizes number of downloads, sets, views	climate change conservation eco-system management	Documentary	Global
38 Underwater protest by Shaama Sandooyee	Climate advocate and scientist Shaama Sandooyee holds a placard reading "Youth Strike For Climate" during an underwater protest in t...	observed by lead users	climate change activist		Mauritius
39 Ich im Wasser, das Wasser in mir	20 young people from Berlin and from the local area in San Luis Potosí, Mexico are dealing artistically with the topic of water through a...	credible curators youth-centred con... observed by lead u...	experiential	Art project	Germany / I
40 Dip in the waters of the river Main - Diversion Esh	The river is a key protagonist in the planetary water cycle—channeling earth's circulation of water from mountain to brook, from ocean...	subjective observation observed by lead users	Stewardship experiential	Art project	Frankfurt ar
41 A short message from AHWE KEHATNE (The Wate	This artist newspaper, edited by Asad Raza and Mathew Hale, accompanies a new work by Raza of the same name, which redirects the...	credible curators biogeographical cont... observed by lead us...	experiential	Art project Newspaper	Global
42 Visões - een avontuur op Salina ("fishes - an advert	Book by Joost Oomen, about an artist residency at Salina. Where Joost Oomen writes a poem for fishes	credible curators youth-centred cont... biogeographical cont... more than human		Book	Mediterran
43 Jonge waterwiskunde ("youth waterwiskunde")	Youngsters' vision on water, written by a (young) climate organisation in NL.	credible curators youth-centred con... observed by lead u...	climate change activist	Article	Netherlands

Figure 3 Snapshot of collaboratively edited list of signals, their description, selection reason, category of relationship, media type and region. For more details, see appendix 1.

Figure 4 Distribution of media types represented in the current signal collection